

INTERFERENCE CORRECTIONS FOR THE GROUPINGS CONTAINING NITROGEN

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The group parachor values for the groups $(C)_2NH$ and $(C)_2N$, and the interference correction for the grouping $C-N-C$ are derived. "Atomic parachor" of nitrogen and the values of the interference corrections for the groupings $C-N-N$, $N-C-N$, and $N-N-N$ are suggested.

Gibling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 146, 151) has suggested that the values of the interference corrections (I.C.) for the groupings $C-C-N$ and $C-N-C$ should be 2.2 and 3.1 respectively. The value of I.C. for the grouping $C-C-N$ was assumed by him from a comparison of the values of I.C. for the groupings $C-C-C$ and $C-C-O$. Although the value for the grouping $C-N-C$ was derived by him by the method used for the calculation of the interference correction for the grouping $C-C-C$ (*ibid.*, 1941, 299), the parachor values used therein appear to have been obtained on certain "assumptions". The present author (*this Journal*, 1955, 32, 799) has shown that the values of I.C. for the groupings $C-C-C$ and $C-C-N$ are of the same order and that the value of the I.C. for the grouping $C-C-X$ will be the same for the elements of the same period in the Periodic Table. Hence it is of importance to know the value of I.C. for the groupings containing nitrogen.

In Table I are presented the compounds, parachor values of which are known and from which R. P. values and R. P. values corrected for I.C. due to $C-C-C$ and $C-C-N$ are calculated for the groups shown therein.

TABLE I

Compounds.	[P] _{obs.}	Group or compound.	R. P.			Group parachor (ideal)
			Calc.	Corr.	Diff.	
Dimethyl amine	139.7	$(CH_3)_2NH$	139.5	139.5	..	..
Diethyl amine	219.6	$(C)CH_2NHCH_2(C)$	108.7	113.1	26.4	115.3
Dipropyl amine	296.2	$(C)_2CHNHCH(C)_2$	73.5	86.7	26.4	88.9
Dibutyl amine	374.3					

The difference between the successive parachor values is constant, *i.e.*, 26.4, which is equal to 2×13.2 . Thus the difference indicates the replacement of two hydrogen atoms. Hence, if we subtract the ideal group parachor values of $CH_3(N)$, $(C)CH_2(N)$ and/or $(C)_2CH(N)$ from the above groups, we shall get the value of $(C)NH(C)$ (uncorrected for $C-N-C$) as 29.1. Now the group parachor value for the group $(C)NH_2$ has been found by the author to be 44.5. Hence the difference between the parachor values of $(C)NH_2$ and $(C)NH(C)$ will be 15.4. This indicates that if the parachor value of hydrogen is taken as 13.2, the value of I.C. for $C-N-C$ will be 2.2, *i.e.*, same as for $C-C-C$ and $C-C-N$. This result indicates that nitrogen atom, whether placed at the end as in $C-C-N$ or in the middle as in $C-N-C$, has the same interference effect.

Ideal group parachor values for these groups are also presented in Table I. Ideal group parachor value for the group $(C)_3CNHC(C)_3$ will be 62.5 and that for $(C)NH(C)$ will be 31.3 [Gibling's value for $(C)NH(C)$ is 35.1].

These results lead us to an idea that C and N atoms behave similarly as regards interference. If this is so, the same value of I.C. will be obtained not only for the groups C—C—N and C—N—C, but also for the groups C—N—N, N—C—N, and N—N—N. It is not possible, however, to derive these values by the present method. Hence by an indirect method the values of these groups may be calculated on the assumption that the value of I.C. for different groups containing C and N is the same, namely, 2.2. For that purpose it will be necessary to calculate the "atomic parachor" value of N.

Atomic Parachor of Nitrogen

Gibling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 299) has mainly worked on the evaluation of the group parachor values and has regarded atomic parachor values derived by the usual method as unsatisfactory. He (*ibid.*, 1945, 236) has, however, calculated the atomic constants for carbon and hydrogen on the basis of the interference concept. He has not so far attempted to calculate the atomic constants for other atoms. For the purpose of arriving at the value of I.C. for C—N—C, he has derived the group parachor values for the groups $(C)NH_2$, $(C)_2NH$, and $(C)_3N$. These values may be utilised to derive the atomic parachor value of nitrogen as shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Group.	Ideal R.P. (Gibling)	Diff.	Ideal R.P. (Talati)	Diff.
$(C)NH_2$	47.9	..	44.5	..
$(C)_2NH$	35.1	12.8	31.3	13.2
$(C)_3N$	22.3	12.8	18.1	13.2

The difference between the successive groups is constant and is 12.8. This indicates that the ideal value of hydrogen in nitrogen compounds may be taken as 12.8. From these values the atomic parachor (ideal) for nitrogen may be calculated as 22.3, I. C. for C—N—C being taken as 3.1.

The author's values for the groups $(C)NH_2$, $(C)_2NH$, and $(C)_3N$ are also shown in Table II. The group parachor value for the group $(C)_3N$ is derived from the known parachor value of trimethyl amine as 11.5. Hence the ideal R.P. for the group will be $11.5+6.6=18.1$.

The difference between the successive ideal R.P. values is constant, namely, 13.2. This indicates that the parachor value of hydrogen in nitrogen compounds is the same as the parachor value of hydrogen in the hydrocarbons. From these results the ideal atomic parachor value for nitrogen is calculated as 18.1.

The values derived from those of present author have an advantage over those obtained by using Gibling's values. Thus the author's considerations lead to an idea that the values of I.C. for C—N—N, N—C—N, and N—N—N should be same as those for C—C—N and C—N—C, *i.e.*, 2.2. Although Gibling obtained different values for I.C. of C—C—N and C—N—C (2.4 and 3.1 respectively), he assumed that in the case of polynitrogen compounds nitrogen atoms produced interferences of the same order as those given by carbon atoms. This assumption contradicts, however, the values obtained by him for C—C—N and C—N—C. Further, his results lead to different atomic parachor values of hydrogen in hydrocarbons and in nitrogen compounds.

Using the author's values, the ideal R.P. values, and uncorrected group parachor values for various groups containing N are calculated as follows (Table III).

TABLE III

Group.	Ideal R.P.	Group parachor (uncorrected).
(N) NH ₂	44.5	44.5
(C) NH (N)	31.3	29.1
(C) N (N) ₂	18.1	11.5
(C) ₂ N(N)	18.1	11.5

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